

Power Smoothing as a Mitigation Action against Rapid Voltage Changes: A Comparative Study

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Abstract—The proliferation of converter-interfaced renewable energy sources (CIRES) in distribution networks (DNs) has necessitated the revision of metrics and practices employed by DN operators (DNOs) to assess and preserve voltage quality within their grids. In this context, a voltage quality index that remains overlooked is that of rapid voltage changes (RVCs). To this end, this paper investigates the impact of volatile CIRES generation on RVCs. The RVCs are quantified based on the definitions of the IEC 61000-4-30:2015 and IEEE 1547:2018 Standards. Additionally, power smoothing (PS) by CIRES, employing an energy storage system (ESS), is introduced as a promising mitigation action. Specifically, three well-established PS methods are compared in terms of their RVC-suppressing capability and the associated stress of the ESS. Moreover, a sensitivity analysis concerning the location of the PS-performing CIRES is conducted. The investigation is performed by means of simulations on the IEEE European Low Voltage (LV) test feeder. The results reveal that the operation of CIRES under a PS scheme can enhance voltage quality by suppressing RVCs.

Index Terms—Converter-interfaced renewable energy sources, power smoothing, rapid voltage changes, voltage quality.

I. INTRODUCTION

CLIMATE change has expedited the adoption of converter-interfaced renewable energy sources (CIRES), introducing new challenges for electricity grids. Focusing on distribution networks (DNs), the volatile generation of CIRES results in high active power ramp rates (RRs), which, in turn, provoke rapid voltage changes (RVCs) [1]. Equipment performance degradation and flickering are the most important issues caused by RVCs, undermining voltage quality within DN [1], [2]. To tackle this, power smoothing (PS) techniques can be integrated into CIRES to reduce high RRs, and, hence, RVCs [3], [4].

In the literature, various PS algorithms have been developed to smooth the injected power of CIRES. In most cases, an energy storage system (ESS) is used to absorb the fast-varying active power of the primary energy sources, e.g., photovoltaic panels (PVs) or wind turbines [5], which operate under maximum power point tracking (MPPT) control. Among the different ESS types, fast-acting ESSs, such as supercapacitors (SCs) [6], are preferred against battery ESSs, since they can effectively support power-intensive actions in small response times [7]. Generally, PS methods are classified into two main categories: filtering and direct ramp-rate limitation

(RRL) algorithms. In filtering methods, the ESS absorbs the high-frequency components of the active power generated by the primary energy source. These high-frequency power components can be identified via one of the following filtering methods: moving average (MA) [8], low-pass filter (LPF) [9], Savitzky-Golay filter [10], and Kalman filter [11]. Conversely, in direct RRL methods, the ESS is employed to saturate the CIRES output power, only when the RR of the primary energy source exceeds a predefined limit [12]–[14], denoted as RR_{lim} .

Although several studies have been dedicated to the techno-economic comparison of PS methods at CIRES level, there is limited literature regarding their impact at grid level, especially their possible contribution to the voltage quality of DN. In [2], the authors focused only on the flickering effect, neglecting the RVC index. Initial investigations to assess the impact of PS on voltage variations were performed in [3], [4]. Nonetheless, these studies were incomplete regarding the RVC definitions and the variety of PS methods considered, while also focusing on simple test cases and not complex DN topologies. Based on the above, the scope of this paper is to highlight the amplifying effect of CIRES volatility on RVCs in real-world DN and demonstrate the aptness of PS techniques for their mitigation. The most well-established PS methods, i.e., MA, LPF, and RRL are considered, while RVCs are defined according to both the IEC 61000-4-30:2015 [15] and the IEEE 1547:2018 [16] Standards. The PS methods are further compared regarding the implied ESS stress. Moreover, a sensitivity analysis for the location of the PS-performing CIRES is conducted. In summary, addressing the literature gaps, the paper thoroughly compares PS techniques at both CIRES level and DN level with respect to RVCs, while also providing insights concerning the relevant standards and the efficient application of PS.

The rest of the manuscript is organized as follows: Section II provides a brief overview of the main PS control approaches. Section III reviews the IEC and IEEE Std. definitions for RVCs. Section IV presents the LV DN under study and describes the examined scenarios. Section V discusses the results. Finally, Section VI concludes the paper with its main findings, and proposes directions for future research.

II. POWER SMOOTHING CONTROL STRATEGIES

In this section, the examined PS strategies are reviewed. The following notations are used: $p_{in}[t]$ for the input power of the MPPT process, $p_{out}^*[t]$ for the desired, smoothed, output power, and $p_{PS}^*[t]$ for the reference power of the ESS, so as to achieve

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Fig. 1. Direct RRL [17], [18].

the desired smoothing effect. In all methods, the equation $p_{PS}^*[t] = p_{in}[t] - p_{out}^*[t]$ holds. Note that $RR_{out}[t]$ stands for the output RR, and Δt for the measurement resolution.

A. Moving Average (MA)

In the MA method, $p_{out}^*[t]$ is set as the average of the N most recent $p_{in}[t]$ values, over a sliding time window of duration Δt_w , as follows [8]:

$$p_{out}^*[t] = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=0}^{N-1} p_{in}[t - i \cdot \Delta t] \quad (1)$$

where $\Delta t_w = \Delta t \cdot (N - 1)$. The smoothing effect depends on N , and, hence, on the choice of Δt_w and the available Δt .

B. Low-pass Filter (LPF)

In the LPF-based methods, $p_{PS}^*[t]$ is determined, so as for $p_{out}^*[t]$ to be a filtered version of $p_{in}[t]$, following a relation equivalent to that of an LPF, with a time constant equal to T_{LPF} . Considering a simple, first-order, discrete-time LPF, the following equation holds in the time domain:

$$T_{LPF} \cdot (p_{out}^*[t] - p_{out}[t - \Delta t]) = \Delta t \cdot (p_{in}[t] - p_{out}^*[t]) \quad (2)$$

Obviously, higher T_{LPF} achieves a better smoothing effect.

C. Direct RRL Control

In direct RRL control approaches, $p_{in}[t]$ is measured, and the corresponding RR, denoted as $RR[t]$, is compared against RR_{lim} , i.e., the desired limit of $RR_{out}[t]$. Specifically, if $|RR[t]| < RR_{lim}$, the ESS does not intervene; otherwise, it injects/absorbs the required energy so that $|RR_{out}[t]| = RR_{lim}$.

In this study, the direct RRL control of [18] is considered. The considered RRL algorithm is depicted in Fig. 1, while a meticulous description is found in [18]. Its inputs are $p_{in}[t]$, and the positive ($max[t] = RR_{lim}$) and negative ($min[t] = -RR_{lim}$) limits of RR_{out} , for ramp-ups and ramp-downs, respectively. These limits are re-adjusted each Δt , depending on the state of charge (SoC). Namely, based on the SoC, the RR_{lim} either obtains a user-defined nominal value, or follows a linear degradation - the ESS operates in an alert area. In that manner, the SoC is *a-priori* considered by re-adjusting the RR_{lim} , to ensure that even when the SoC approaches its limits, the PS service is still provided. The output of the control block is the smoothed power $p_{out}[t]$, by which the reference power, $p_{PS}^*[t]$, is determined.

III. REVIEW OF EXISTING STANDARDS FOR RVCs

This section presents the RVC definitions of the IEC 61000-4-30:2015-Class A [15] and IEEE 1547:2018 Standards [16].

Fig. 2. Indicative RVC event according to [15].

A. IEC 61000-4-30 Std

The IEC 61000-4-30:2015 Std [15]-Class A defines RVCs over a reference time interval, Δt_{ref} , of 1-s and is based on the $U_{rms(1/2)}$ magnitude, i.e., the RMS value of the voltage, measured over one cycle, and refreshed each half-cycle. Thus, Δt_{ref} accounts for M calculated values of $U_{rms(1/2)}$, where $M=100/120$ for 50/60 Hz systems, respectively. The monitored voltage is in steady-state, if all the M preceding $U_{rms(1/2)}$ values lie within a dynamic threshold, $th(\%)$, calculated as a percentage of their arithmetic mean, $U_{rms(1/2)}^{mean}$ [1]. Hence, an RVC event begins if at least one of the M preceding values exceeds the threshold. Note that, during an RVC event, a hysteresis is applied at th . Percentages from 1% to 6% of $U_{rms(1/2)}$ for the detection threshold, $th(\%)$; and around 50% of th , for the hysteresis, are suggested. Therefore, no specific guideline exists and both parameters are user-defined.

An RVC is quantified in [15] by three parameters: duration (ΔT), magnitude (ΔU_{ss}), and maximum deviation (ΔU_{max}). ΔU_{ss} is the absolute difference between the final $U_{rms(1/2)}^{mean}$ value prior to the event and the first $U_{rms(1/2)}^{mean}$ value after the event. ΔU_{max} represents the maximum absolute difference between any of the $U_{rms(1/2)}$ values, during the RVC event, and the final $U_{rms(1/2)}^{mean}$ value, before the event. Essentially, ΔU_{ss} and ΔU_{max} express the intensity of an RVC incident. ΔT is defined as $\Delta T = t_r - t_s - \Delta t_{ref}$, where t_s and t_r are the commencing and the steady-state restoration instants of the event, respectively. If the RVC magnitude is higher than $\pm 10\%$ of nominal voltage, the variation is not considered an RVC, but a voltage swell or dip, respectively. For a better comprehension of the detection process, the reader is referred to Fig. 2, where an indicative RVC event is identified. Here, $th=1\%$, while UB , LB stand for the upper and lower boundary of $U_{rms(1/2)}$, respectively.

B. IEEE 1547-2018 Std

The IEEE 1547:2018 Std [16] states that an individual CIRES, at medium-voltage level, shall not cause step or ramp changes in the RMS voltage exceeding 3% of nominal and 3%/s, averaged over a period of 1-s. The respective limit is 5% for the LV level. Nevertheless, when referring to the combined effect of all the RVC-inducing sources, the Standard uses the stricter limit of 3% for both voltage levels. Concerning the detection process, no specific directive is provided.

Fig. 3. IEEE European LV test feeder [19].

Fig. 4. PV profile used in the simulations.

TABLE I
PV NOMINAL POWER

P_{pv} (kW _p)	Node
30	845, 869, 882, 884
20	70, 73, 234, 248, 453, 461, 476, 482, 604, 619, 794,
15	247, 320, 447, 651, 785, 861
10	166, 219, 388, 403, 556, 567, 578, 580, 588, 681, 763

IV. SYSTEM UNDER STUDY

In this section, the LV DN under study and the CIRES modeling approaches are introduced. Subsequently, this section provides an overview of the different operational scenarios considered and the comparisons conducted in Section V.

A. LV DN Topology and Load Modeling Approach

The RVC-suppressing capability of the PS schemes is evaluated by means of dynamic RMS simulations, executed through Powerfactory, on the IEEE European LV test feeder [19], illustrated in Fig. 3. It comprises 906 nodes and 50 three-phase residential loads, that are modeled as ohmic and constant-power. The loads are assigned an abrupt active power profile, derived from the real, three-year household consumption data of [20], available in [21]. The short circuit capacity of the upstream feeder is 63 MVA. The total installed power of the loads and the rating of the transformer are 800 kVA. The nominal voltage of the DN is 0.416 kV.

B. CIRES Modeling Approach

To examine scenarios of high CIRES penetration, 32 three-phase PVs were dispersed across the DN, with a total installed capacity of 540 kW_p. The nominal power and the location of the PVs are mapped in Table I. The PVs were simulated according to two different models:

Model#1: conventional MPPT-controlled CIRES, without PS functionalities.

Model#2: PS-performing CIRES, through a voltage source converter (VSC) equipped with an SC. Specifically, the VSC analyzed in [21], [22] is considered. The SC size (in Wh) is determined according to the economic evaluation of [17], as a function of the CIRES rated power.

For the input active power, the profile of Fig. 4 is employed, deriving from the volatile PV power measurements of [17] and, specifically, from the 1200-s window with the most severe power variations. On the same plot, the corresponding RRs can be observed. For both profiles, $\Delta t=1$ s.

C. Examined Cases

For the comparison of the PS methods with respect to their impact on RVCs and the effect of the penetration of PS-performing CIRES, the following cases are considered:

Case 1 (No PS): Initially, the 32 PVs are simulated according to Model#1, i.e., without PS functionality. In the absence of PS control, this benchmark case serves to highlight the voltage quality degradation caused by CIRES and to compare the RVC definitions of the two Standards.

Case 2 (PS by all PVs): In this scenario, Model#2 is considered for the PVs. Three subcases are distinguished based on the utilized PS scheme, as follows:

Case 2a: The RRL scheme of [18], with $RR_{lim}=0.01$ pu/s.

Case 2b: The LPF method of (2), with $T_{LPF}=52$ s.

Case 2c: The MA method of (1), with $\Delta t_w=72$ s.

For the direct RRL method, $RR_{lim}=0.01$ pu/s was selected as a relatively lax target value, corresponding to 60%/min, i.e., 6 times more relaxed than the widely-used limit of 10%/min [2], [23]. Accordingly, $T_{LPF}=52$ s and $\Delta t_w=72$ s were selected for the LPF and the MA methods, respectively, as the minimum values for which the RR_{out} is retained within the limits of [-0.01 pu/s, 0.01 pu/s] of the direct RRL method, ensuring a fair comparison among the three techniques.

Overall, Case 2 enables a holistic comparison of the three primary PS methods; both at CIRES level, according to the implied ESS fatigue, and at DN level, assessing the effectiveness of the methods in mitigating RVCs.

Case 3 (Direct RRL by 50% of PVs): In this scenario, 50% of the PVs are modeled as Model#1 and 50% as Model#2, employing the direct RRL method. Three subcases are distinguished (Fig. 5), to examine the impact of the topology of the CIRES mixture on the RVCs:

- **Case 3a:** The 16 Model#1 PVs and the 16 Model#2 PVs are uniformly distributed across the DN.

- **Case 3b:** Model#2 is used for the 16 most remote, from the substation, PVs.

- **Case 3c:** Model#2 is used for the 16 most proximal, to the substation, PVs.

Case 3 regards a sensitivity analysis of the RVC mitigation with respect to the location of the PS-performing CIRES. This analysis is conducted from the perspective of the DNO, aiming to optimize the placement of Model#2 CIRES within a DN.

The results are presented for six representative nodes, i.e., Nodes 882, 639, 619, 101, 373, and 467, shown in Fig. 3. The total simulation time is 1200 s and the simulation step is 1 ms.

Fig. 5. Topologies of Case 3 in the IEEE European LV test feeder.

TABLE II
RVCs ACCORDING TO IEC STD FOR CASE 1

th	Node 882			Node 639			Node 619		
	N	ΔU_{\max}	ΔU_{ss}	N	ΔU_{\max}	ΔU_{ss}	N	ΔU_{\max}	ΔU_{ss}
4%	1	4.29	4.29	1	4.12	4.12	1	4.2	4.2
3%	9	4.75	4.33	7	4.54	4.17	7	4.57	4.2
2%	23	5.23	5.19	21	5.01	4.98	21	5.04	5.01
1%	59	5.93	5.62	55	5.79	5.49	55	5.83	5.53
th	Node 101			Node 373			Node 467		
	N	ΔU_{\max}	ΔU_{ss}	N	ΔU_{\max}	ΔU_{ss}	N	ΔU_{\max}	ΔU_{ss}
4%	0	-	-	0	-	-	1	3.33	1.64
3%	0	-	-	1	3.2	3.2	4	4.29	3.96
2%	1	1.93	1.93	12	3.75	3.23	19	4.75	4.17
1%	18	2.3	2.07	45	3.86	3.84	53	5.45	5.17

V. SIMULATION RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In this section, the results for the representative cases are presented and thoroughly discussed. Specifically, for distinct th (%) values, the total number of events, N , and the maximum values of ΔU_{ss} (%), ΔU_{\max} (%) for those N events, are recorded. Each case allows for a distinct comparative analysis.

A. Case 1 (No PS) - Voltage Quality Degradation and Standards Comparison

The RVCs detected according to the IEC Std. are aggregated in Table II. As shown, in the case of rapidly varying CIRES power, the voltage quality in an LV DN is jeopardized, with numerous RVCs arising. For a certain node, the number of detected events strongly depends on the strictness of the user-defined threshold, with lower th values resulting in a higher number of events. Furthermore, for a certain threshold, the number and intensity of the RVC events increase, as the distance from the substation increases.

For the sake of comparison, Table III presents the RVCs according to the IEEE Std. For each examined node, the total number of events, N , and the maximum RoCoV ($\frac{\Delta V}{\Delta t}$ (%/s)), measured for these N events, are displayed. Note that, abiding by the Standard, the calculated RoCoV is the average RoCoV, over the 1-s analysis period. Comparing the results of Table III with their equivalent results of Table II (i.e., for $th=3\%$), it is deduced that both Standards detect the same number of events. Overall, up to 9 RVCs were recorded, for a time period of 1200-s (i.e., 1/3 of an hour). As a comparison, the IEEE Std. limits the allowable number of events to only $2 \leq N \leq 10$ per hour. Therefore, the conducted simulations emphasize

TABLE III
RVCs ACCORDING TO IEEE STD FOR CASE 1

N	Node 882	Node 639	Node 619	Node 101	Node 373	Node 467
	$\frac{\Delta V}{\Delta t}$	4.28	4.18	4.21	-	3.33

the importance of implementing measures to mitigate RVCs, considering that the results are based on actual PV power measurements and expose the vulnerability of LV DNs to voltage fluctuations. Proceeding with the Standards, the ΔU_{ss} parameter of the IEC Std. holds similar values with the $\frac{\Delta V}{\Delta t}$ parameter of the IEEE Std. Consequently, as the Standards lead to equivalent results, only the IEC Std. will be used for the remainder of this paper, thanks to its more thorough detection process and quantification of the RVCs. Furthermore, the strictest value of $th=1\%$ will be adopted henceforth, as it allows for a more reliable and safe assessment of the events.

B. Case 2 (PS by all PVs) - Analysis at CIRES level

In this scenario, Model#2 is considered for the PVs, operating under the three examined PS algorithms. First, the three methods are compared at CIRES level, with respect to the achieved containment of RR_{out} and the implied stress of the ESS. As observed in Fig. 4, the maximum absolute input RR value is 0.228 pu/s, with the target RR_{lim} of 0.01 pu/s being exceeded for 26.75% of the analysis period. The achieved $RR_{out}[t]$ (pu/s) for each PS method is depicted in Fig. 6, along with the benchmark input RR. Although the RR-limiting effect of the employed methods is clear, several violations of the target RR_{lim} are observed. This deviation from the theoretical smoothing effect is due to the technical constraints of the VSC and the SC, e.g., rated power, finite capacitance, and operating voltage range. The SC power (pu) and SoC (pu) are represented in Figs. 7a, 7b, respectively. Observing Fig. 6 and Fig. 7, the following conclusions are drawn: (a) The LPF and MA methods result in unnecessary over-smoothing, visible in Fig. 6. The corresponding excessive SC charging/discharging is evident in Fig. 7a and accounts for higher SoC values, as shown in Fig. 7b. (b) Consequently, this unnecessary charging/discharging might stress the SC to its operational limits, even when the input RRs are low. This stressing could render the SC incapable of absorbing/injecting the required energy to contain the output RR, leading to more significant RR_{lim} violations than the direct RRL method.

Fig. 6. PV Output RR (pu/s) for each considered model.

Fig. 7. SC Power (a) and SoC (b) for each PS method

TABLE IV
RVCs AT NODE 882 ACCORDING TO IEC STD FOR CASES 2A-2B

		Node 882 - Case 2a			Node 882 - Case 2b		
th	N	ΔU_{max}	ΔU_{ss}	N	ΔU_{max}	ΔU_{ss}	
1%	1	1.31	1.17	1	1.31	1.16	

TABLE V
RVCs ACCORDING TO IEC STD FOR CASE 2C

		Node 882			Node 639			Node 619		
th	N	ΔU_{max}	ΔU_{ss}	N	ΔU_{max}	ΔU_{ss}	N	ΔU_{max}	ΔU_{ss}	
1%	3	1.38	1.26	1	1.34	1.22	1	1.32	1.2	
		Node 101			Node 373			Node 467		
th	N	ΔU_{max}	ΔU_{ss}	N	ΔU_{max}	ΔU_{ss}	N	ΔU_{max}	ΔU_{ss}	
1%	0	-	-	1	1.14	1.05	1	1.19	1.09	

C. Case 2 (PS by all PVs) - RVC mitigation

In Case 2a, the application of the proposed RRL scheme eliminates almost all RVC events detected for Case 1. As shown in Table IV, only one event was detected, at Node 882. Therefore, the usage of direct RRL control, with a relatively loose target RR_{lim} , achieves the effective elimination of RVCs.

Similar results are obtained for Case 2b. The LPF method effectively eradicates the RVCs as well, with only one event remaining, at Node 882, as shown in Table IV. The RVC suppression is visually confirmed via Fig. 8. Fig. 8a presents the voltage at Node 882, for Cases 1-2, with the reduction of the slope being evident. The achieved decrease in RoCoV is better illustrated in Fig. 8b. Moreover, Fig. 8b attests that the unnecessary over-smoothing effect of the LPF method is pronounced in the node voltages as well. Nevertheless, voltage

Fig. 8. Voltage (a) and RoCoV (b) at Node 882 for Cases 1-2.

TABLE VI
RVCs ACCORDING TO IEC STD FOR CASE 3A

		Node 882			Node 639			Node 619		
th	N	ΔU_{max}	ΔU_{ss}	N	ΔU_{max}	ΔU_{ss}	N	ΔU_{max}	ΔU_{ss}	
1%	18	2.76	2.57	21	2.88	2.72	21	2.93	2.77	
		Node 101			Node 373			Node 467		
th	N	ΔU_{max}	ΔU_{ss}	N	ΔU_{max}	ΔU_{ss}	N	ΔU_{max}	ΔU_{ss}	
1%	0	-	-	7	1.66	1.42	18	2.71	2.56	

TABLE VII
RVCs ACCORDING TO IEC STD FOR CASE 3B

		Node 882			Node 639			Node 619		
th	N	ΔU_{max}	ΔU_{ss}	N	ΔU_{max}	ΔU_{ss}	N	ΔU_{max}	ΔU_{ss}	
1%	3	1.54	1.29	3	1.73	1.45	3	1.72	1.42	
		Node 101			Node 373			Node 467		
th	N	ΔU_{max}	ΔU_{ss}	N	ΔU_{max}	ΔU_{ss}	N	ΔU_{max}	ΔU_{ss}	
1%	0	-	-	2	1.28	1.2	3	1.70	1.42	

quality was not further improved, as the LPF method did not manage to eliminate the remaining event of Case 2. This is attributed to the impeded smoothing effect of the SC, due to the previously explained excessive stress.

This phenomenon is even more extreme for the MA method, which presents deficient performance regarding the RVC elimination. As shown in Table V, the method failed to suppress seven RVC events in total, in three out of the six monitored nodes. The higher RoCoV values in Fig. 8b affirm this finding.

In conclusion, the direct RRL and the LPF methods present equivalent performance regarding the suppression of RVCs. However, the direct RRL method achieves this performance with reduced SC stress in terms of power and charging/discharging cycles, hence ensuring a longer SC lifetime. Thus, the RRL method is more beneficial investment-wise.

D. Case 3 (Direct RRL in 50% of PVs) - Sensitivity Analysis

Provided that the 100% penetration of the RRL-performing CIRES proved to effectively restore voltage quality within the DN, the case of 50% penetration is examined, for different topologies. Tables VI, VII, VIII showcase the impact of topology, for the same penetration level. Namely, in Case 3a, where

TABLE VIII
RVCs ACCORDING TO IEC STD FOR CASE 3C

		Node 882		Node 639			Node 619		
th	N	ΔU_{max}	ΔU_{ss}	N	ΔU_{max}	ΔU_{ss}	N	ΔU_{max}	ΔU_{ss}
1%	42	3.84	3.71	33	3.43	3.31	34	3.47	3.35
		Node 101		Node 373			Node 467		
th	N	ΔU_{max}	ΔU_{ss}	N	ΔU_{max}	ΔU_{ss}	N	ΔU_{max}	ΔU_{ss}
1%	0	-	-	15	2.39	2.77	28	3.15	3.02

the Model#1 and Model#2 PVs are uniformly distributed across the DN, the number and the intensity of events are reduced by at least 60%, compared to Case 1. By contrast, Case 3b presents similar findings to Case 2, i.e., almost complete suppression of RVCs, because Model#2 PVs were installed at the most distant, and, thus, most critical nodes. The opposite phenomenon appears in Case 3c, where only a 35%-45% reduction, with respect to Case 1, is achieved. This limited effect is attributed to the placement of conventional PVs at the most distant nodes, leaving them vulnerable to voltage variations. Therefore, according to the results of Case 1 and Case 3b, from the DNO perspective, similar RVC mitigation can be achieved, with only 50% deployment of PS-performing CIRES- and thus with only 50% of the expenditure of Case 2a – as long as they are installed at the remote nodes.

VI. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE RESEARCH

In this paper, the issue of RVCs is brought into focus, and PS techniques are evaluated as a potential mitigation action. More specifically, three main PS techniques, i.e., the MA, the LPF, and the RRL methods, are evaluated in terms of their RVC-suppressing capability on the IEEE European LV DN. The evaluation is based on the IEC 61000-4-30:2015 and IEEE 1547:2018 Stds. The findings demonstrate that all PS techniques can improve the voltage quality within the DN, mitigating the RVCs that occur due to rapid variations of CIRES active power. However, at CIRES level, the LPF and the MA approaches perform over-smoothing, and thus lead to excessive SC stress, compared to the RRL control. In addition, a sensitivity analysis is performed regarding the location of CIRES operating with RRL control, showcasing that the RVC suppression is more efficient when the CIRES located at the most remote nodes are equipped with PS schemes. The conducted analysis could pave the way for the recognition of the RVC elimination via RRL control as a new ancillary service. Future research will focus on the development of a strategy for the optimal employment of PS by DNOs, with the CIRES topology and penetration level as parameters.

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